

SEAFAC THE NAVY'S PREMIER ACOUSTIC MEASUREMENT FACILITY

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Abstract - National and economic security depend on sea control. To help assure that our nation meets these objectives, U.S. Navy submarines must be able to operate anywhere, at any time, undetected. Carderock Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center (CARDEROCK-DIV, NSWC), formerly the David Taylor Research Center (DTRC), is responsible for maintaining the acoustic superiority of our submarines. The Southeast Alaska Acoustic Measurement Facility (SEAFAC) was designed to "check the health of stealth." Its mission is to measure and reduce the noise from submarines.

Increased acoustic interference at current facilities and the design of progressively quieter submarines led the Navy to search for a new measurement site. SEAFAC, the Navy's newest facility for assessing submarine vulnerability is located in western Behm Canal, near Ketchikan, Alaska. Behm Canal is a relatively quiet body of water, where the noise environment does not interfere with listening activi-

ties. Behm Canal is also deep and large enough for submarine operations.

In this unique location, CARDEROCKDIV, NSWC has built a facility designed around the most advanced measurement technology available to acquire, process and evaluate submarine signatures. Superior support systems, utilities, special project accommodations, intermediate maintenance level mechanical and electrical shops, and large lay down areas make SEAFAC as self-sufficient as possible in the intense, remote work environment of southeast Alaska.

"If you have stealth, you will win. If you don't, you will lose", says VADM Roger F. Bacon, Vice Chief of Naval Operations for Submarines. An ideal location, state-of-the-art acoustic technology, and a solid support structure combine to make SEAFAC the Navy's premier underwater acoustic measurement facility.

SEAFAC, located near Ketchikan, Alaska

I. INTRODUCTION

The United States has a continuing program to reduce the noise signatures of its submarines. The capability to accurately measure submarine radiated noise is essential to defining their vulnerability, as well as providing input for future submarine designs.

Carderock Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center, Detachment Puget Sound (NSWC DET Puget Sound) operates two West Coast facilities which perform submarine acoustic measurements, the Carr Inlet Acoustic Range (CIAR) and the Santa Cruz Acoustic Range Facility (SCARF). CIAR, near Tacoma, Washington, was established in the 1950's and designed for WWII vintage diesel submarines which operated at slower speeds and shallower depths than modern nuclear ones. SCARF, a deep, open ocean site near Santa Barbara, California, was designed to accommodate all submarine operations and obtain higher speed data. By the late 1970's, it became increasingly difficult to perform certain acoustic tests at either of these ranges. Two factors eroded their capability to measure submarine noise: the dramatic reductions in submarine signatures and more frequent ambient noise interference. If future submarine designs were to be adequately measured a quieter test environment and improved measurement technologies were needed.

In 1980, a thorough search of Pacific U.S. territorial waters was made to identify potential sites. Operational underwater acoustic test sites in the eastern and central Pacific were re-evaluated. Hydrographic charts and coastal area records were reviewed for possible, new locations. The selection criteria were heavily based on physical characteristics. Was the site quiet enough for acoustic testing? Was it accessible? Was it large enough for a submarine to safely operate?

In 1981, the Naval Sea Systems Command (NAVSEA-SYSCOM) initiated the Acoustic Measurement Facilities Improvement Program (AMFIP) to ensure that Navy facilities would meet future requirements. The major elements of AMFIP included upgrades to existing acoustic ranges, the development of new measurement technologies, and the construction of a new West Coast measurement facility.

Of all the potential West Coast sites, Behm Canal in southeast Alaska proved the most promising. Behm Canal is a protected fjord, large and deep enough for submarine operations. This remote site is located in the rain and wind shadow of the surrounding mountains. It does not experience the severe wind and high sea states of the open ocean. It is not near any major shipping channel nor is it likely that

Back Island shore complex

such traffic will increase there. Behm Canal also offered a suitable location on Back Island for shore facilities.

After a decade of development, the Southeast Alaska Acoustic Measurement Facility (SEAFAC) was dedicated on 7 November 1991 and hosted its first submarine acoustic trial in March 1992.

II. DESCRIPTION

A. SEAFAC Systems

SEAFAC consists of several major systems: the Radiated Energy Signal Acquisition System (RESAS), the Signal Conditioning and Distribution System (SCDS), the Signal Processing and Data Analysis System (SPDAS), and the SEAFAC Tracking and Navigation System (STANAS). When integrated, these systems constitute the SEAFAC Measurement System.

1) *Radiated Energy Signal Acquisition System (RESAS):* The measurement arrays located in the center of the Underway Site are the main components of the Radiated Energy Signal Acquisition System (RESAS). The two RESAS arrays receive the radiated acoustic energy from the test submarine and transmit that data by 12-quad, armored signal cables directly to the measurement system in the Operations Center. The cable lengths are 28,488 feet for RESAS-West and 26,805 feet for RESAS-East. The arrays are separated by 250 yards and held vertically in the water column by subsurface buoys. Each RESAS array has a recovery system.

2) *Signal Conditioning and Distribution System (SCDS):* The Signal Conditioning and Distribution System (SCDS)

terminates, conditions, distributes, and records signals received from all in-water arrays. SCDS provides power to the sensor array electronics and the sensor array calibrators. Received signals are amplified, filtered and distributed to the signal processing, tracking, recording, and data monitoring subsystems.

3) *Signal Processing and Data Analysis System (SPDAS)*: The Signal Processing and Data Analysis System has two functions: (1) converting the acoustic signals to digital data, and (2) displaying the processed data for analysis. Array signals are converted to one-third octave and narrowband data, or subjected to specialized processing. After the system calibration is applied, data are range-corrected for on-line analysis, then stored for post-processing.

4) *SEAFAC Tracking and Navigation Aids System (STANAS)*: The SEAFAC Tracking and Navigation Aids System (STANAS) determines the distance between the submerged submarine's acoustic center and every sensor on each of the radiated noise measurement arrays. This information is not only sent to SPDAS, but is necessary for the safe navigation in the Underway Operating Area. STANAS also generates an acoustic Underwater Emergency Warning System (UEWS) signal if the submarine strays out of the operating area or if underwater telephone (WQC) communications are lost.

5) *Communications*: SEAFAC operations are supported by an integrated communications network. A fully redundant, underwater telephone is the main link between submarine and the Operations Center. The radio suite includes secure voice, UHF, VHF, Marine band, and CB networks. Two other dedicated VHF working nets facilitate essential maintenance and operations.

6) *Surveillance*: SEAFAC maintains surface surveillance of its range areas for operational safety as well as perimeter area surveillance for security. Radar monitors vessel traffic in the operating areas and can communicate that data to STANAS. Video surveillance cameras are placed around the compound, pier and in several secure areas. An environmental monitoring system records weather and sea conditions during operations.

B. Underway Site

Submarines travel to the Naval Submarine Base at Bangor, Washington for installation of trial equipment. NSWC DET Puget Sound personnel board at this time and conduct a variety of pre-trial tests as the ship makes its two day trek to SEAFAC. When the submarine arrives, the ship's crew familiarizes themselves with the range systems before

testing begins. A typical trial lasts 3 - 5 days depending upon the type of data required.

At the Underway Site, sounds from a submarine are measured while it is moving through the water. The underway operating area is 5,000 yards wide, 12,000 yards long and 1,300 feet deep. At all times, STANAS maintains a precise track of the submarine as it maneuvers between the RESAS arrays. The submarine makes numerous passes between these arrays under a variety of operating conditions, speeds, and depths. SEAFAC operations are identical to those at other Pacific Fleet facilities. The only significant difference for a ship's crew familiar with CIAR and SCARF is the SEAFAC topography. Every submarine is assigned a shipboard Trial Coordinator during operations. He advises the Commanding Officer on navigation, communications, and the sequence of testing.

Range lights alert local traffic that SEAFAC is operational. The lights advise boaters that tests are in progress and that they must coordinate their passage with SEAFAC Control. The amber range lights are visible at four miles in daylight and sixteen miles at night. They flash for 5 seconds every minute.

C. Static Site

The Static Site (Fig. 1) consists of an anchor and mooring system, a power barge (YRPB-2), four sheave buoys, and a suspension barge (YFN-1259). This system positions a submarine for submerging in place, lowers it to depths for testing, holds it stationary, and then, raises the submarine to periscope depth for normal surfacing. Four suspension cables are used for lowering the submarine: two from the suspension barge, and two from the power barge. Four large corner buoys are anchored in a rectangle, 1,200 feet by 750 feet. Each buoy is anchored to the sea bed by a two point mooring. At each end of the rectangle, a compliant span wire with sinker will connect two corner buoys. The sinker displaces the span wire to a depth of 187 feet to allow a submarine to enter the Static Site.

The SEAFAC Static Site will be installed in the summer of 1993 and replace the CIAR Static Site, the only other such facility in the U.S. The Static Site allows controlled measurements of submarine systems without propulsion related noise. The Static Site arrays will be similar to the RESAS arrays. They will be separated by 250 yards and be able to simultaneously measure the port and starboard radiated noise signatures. However, the hydrophone signals from these arrays will be brought directly to an on-water laboratory space on the power barge. From there the signals will be transmitted to shore via a fiber optic link for processing and analysis. Fiber optics are also used for com-

Fig. 1. SEAFAC Static Site

munications (such as a telephone line for the suspended submarine or a secure intercom with the SEAFAC laboratory), and control signals for suspension operations (e.g., monitoring cable tensions).

D. Back Island Shore Complex

The SEAFAC shore complex on the northwestern side of Back Island supports the underwater acoustic measurement facility. The Operations Compound consists of a pier, boat ramp and three buildings: the Range Operations Building, the Utility Building, and the Storage Building.

1) *Range Operations Building:* The Range Operations Building is the center for coordination of all SEAFAC activities. It consists of three sections. The front section facing Behm Canal is a two story, concrete building that contains all vital equipment, instrumentation, and support systems. A 10 ohm equi-potential ground plane is provided under the building and the entire compound. The laboratory, analysis areas, conference and communications rooms, and computer vault all meet the strictest security requirements. An electronics shop is adjacent to these spaces. The middle section is single story, frame construction that contains the kitchen, messing, and common areas. The last section is also single story, frame construction for bunk rooms, bathrooms, and living spaces. Berthing is similar in style to that found on ship. There are eight double bunks in an open bay for temporary quarters and twelve staterooms. Each stateroom sleeps two. Two staterooms share one bath. SEAFAC has total accommodations for 40 scientists and engineers who will travel there 10 - 15 times each year to conduct the measurements on a 24-hr a day basis.

SEAFAC Range Operations

From the laboratory, NSWC DET Puget Sound personnel conduct the acoustic trial. The Trial Director is senior watchstander and is responsible for range safety. His workstation provides him with the communications, range surveillance, and monitoring equipment necessary to oversee trial operations. The Tracking Operator, who is specifically responsible for the operation and functioning of the tracking system, has a dedicated workstation. The Measurement System Operator controls, configures, and operates the data acquisition and analysis systems. The Lead Analyst monitors the incoming radiated noise signals, checks the quality of acquired and processed data and supervises two other radiated noise specialists. Each subordinate analyst mans a workstation to accurately analyze and evaluate the acquired radiated noise data.

2) *Utility Building:* The Utilities Building is a heated, single story steel building that provides services to the Operations Building. It contains most of SEAFAC's support systems such as the emergency diesel generators, heating system, water purification system, fire pumps, laundry room, trash compactor, and mechanical shop. This maintenance shop has welding gear, lathes, sheetmetal equipment, and woodworking tools. Vehicle and small boat maintenance is done in a covered work bay. Potable water is collected from the roofs of the Range Operations and Utility Buildings. Raw rain water is stored in a 100,000 gallon storage tank, which also supplies the fire-fighting and sprinkler systems.

3) *Storage Building:* The Storage Building is a single story steel building that provides covered storage for equipment. It has a large interior area. The building is insulated, but not heated. It serves as a shipping and receiving office.

4) *Special Project Accommodations:* To support future projects or special, one-of-a-kind testing requirements, two trailer pads are available. Trailers can be brought in by barge and provided not only with utilities but also with signals from the measurement arrays, thus allowing visiting researchers the ability to set up fully independent data processing and analysis systems.

5) *Electrical Power Services:* Electrical power for the SEAFAC facility is provided from a Ketchikan Public Utilities (KPU) substation at Settlers Cove. A power cable connects to the transmission line at Settlers Cove and brings power under Clover Passage to Back Island. An underground cable crosses Back Island to the power substation in the Operations Compound. The SEAFAC substation is the terminus of the 12.5 KV transmission line. Two diesel generators provide emergency power if KPU service fails. Each generator can provide 500 KW of power at 480 volts, three phase. This is sufficient power for the Measurement System and all other shore loads. The emergency generators come on line within 30 seconds of an outage. Two redundant power conditioners provide clean power for the measurement system and isolate it from power line noise and transients. Three Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS) provide power for all vital equipment, such as WQC, STANAS, and UEWS. Each UPS has the capacity to support a 15 KVA load for 15 minutes.

6) *Pier and Dock:* A pier and dock are provided for access to Back Island for equipment and personnel. The main pier can accommodate ships and barges transferring supplies and material to the island. A boat ramp is also provided for hauling boats out of the water for storage, maintenance or protection from winter storms. There are three pier cranes. One crane is used to raise the pedestrian gangway out of the water. (Static lift capacity: 20,000 pounds; Minimum hook speed: 20 feet per minute; Reach: 9.5 feet.) A bridge crane with travelling

gantry is located above the floating dock and is used to raise and lower the floating dock. (Static lift capacity -20,000 pounds. Minimum hook speed - 20 feet per minute.) The main crane is a telescoping boom crane. It is pedestal mounted and has a 360 degree continuous rotation. The boom consists of a 30 foot main section and a 20 foot extension. The boom can elevate 0 to 80 degrees. (Static lift capacity - 30,000 pounds at a radius of 25 feet minimum. Minimum hook speed - 40 feet per minute.)

7) *Fuel Storage:* SEAFAC uses diesel fuel for heating, work vehicles, boats and the emergency generators. Two above ground, double walled tanks are provided for the storage of fuel oil. Each tank has a capacity of 7,000 gallons. In addition, 500 gallon day tanks are provided at the dock and the Utility Building.

8) *Compound Security:* A closed circuit television system monitors the dock and pier area, the compound, and access to the secure section of the Range Operations Building. Video surveillance cameras will also be located on the Power Barge for operational surveillance of the Static Site. An intrusion detection system with infrared detectors monitors access into and out of sensitive areas in the Range Operation Building and the Utilities Building. Entrance into secure areas is controlled by a keypad access system. These electronic door locks require that individual access codes be entered on the scramble pad.

III. SUMMARY

SEAFAC is designed to easily implement new measurement technology and various other improvements occurring within the acoustic measurement community. The U.S. Navy's ability to conduct its quality assurance of stealth is assured for today and for tomorrow's generation of quiet submarines.